

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10693734>

Report on the literature search and climate suitability analysis of African *Leucinodes* spp.

Eugenio Rossi, Ewelina Czwieniczek, Julia Lopez Mercadal, Wopke Van der Werf, Alan MacLeod, Richard Mally, Alex Gobbi, Dejana Golic, Marika De Santis, Andrea Maiorano

Abstract

Climate suitability analysis allows to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest. This analysis is typically based on pest ecophysiology and/or distribution and can be done using different methodologies and models. In the context of an EFSA pest risk assessment on African *Leucinodes* spp., a climate suitability analysis was performed. The current publication includes: (i) a report on the extensive literature search conducted to retrieve data and information on the pest and on the methodology of the climate suitability analysis, (ii) an excel file including metadata on the literature analysed, (iii) an excel file including the observed distribution data of the African *Leucinodes* spp., (iv) maps related to the climate suitability analysis of African *Leucinodes* spp., (v) a Geopackage including the layers related to the climate suitability analysis (vi) a .zip folder containing the QGIS styles used to produce the maps.

© European Food Safety Authority, 2024

Keywords: (climate suitability, pest risk assessment, pest distribution, African *Leucinodes* spp., Brinjal fruit borer, Eggplant fruit and shoot borer, climate change)

Suggested citation: Rossi, E., Czwienczek, E., Lopez Mercadal, J., Van Der Werf, W., MacLeod, A., Mally, R., Gobbi, A., Golic, D., De Santis, M., & Maiorano, A. (2024). EFSA Climate Suitability Analysis of African Leucinodes spp. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10693734>

© European Food Safety Authority, 2024

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

EFSA may include images or other content for which it does not hold copyright. In such cases, EFSA indicates the copyright holder and users should seek permission to reproduce the content from the original source.

Table of contents

Abstract	1
Table of contents.....	3
1. Introduction	4
2. Note on this report	4
3. Data and methodologies	4
3.1. Systematic literature search & pest distribution	4
3.2. Document screening and data extraction.....	4
3.3. Data analysis.....	5
3.3.1. Köppen–Geiger climate classification analysis	5
3.3.2. CLIMEX.....	6
3.3.3. Identification of NUTS2 regions in Europe.....	6
4. Results	8
4.1. Document screening and data extraction.....	8
4.2. Pest distribution.....	9
4.3. Köppen–Geiger climate matching	11
4.4. CLIMEX.....	12
4.4.1. Current climate scenario	12
4.4.2. Climate change scenarios.....	14
4.5. Identification of NUTS2 regions at potential risk of establishment.....	16
References	18
Content of the African <i>Leucinodes</i> spp. Zenodo repository	19
Appendix A – Additional figures	21

1. Introduction

Climate suitability analysis allows risk assessors to identify regions where climate is likely to support the establishment of a pest (IPPC, 2013). This analysis is typically based on pest biology and/or distribution and makes use of a variety of methodologies and models (Devorshak, 2012). An extensive literature search, in accordance with EFSA systematic review methodology (EFSA, 2010), was performed to gather relevant information on the pest distribution, physiology-ecology, hosts, biology, control methods, spread, and impact for *Leucinodes* species occurring in Africa (hereafter African *Leucinodes* spp.). Then, the data extracted after the literature search were used to analyse the climate suitability and potential establishment of African *Leucinodes* spp. in the EU.

2. Note on this report

This document includes a description of the methodology and results of the systematic literature search and climate suitability analysis developed in the context of the EFSA Scientific Opinion on *Leucinodes* spp. from Africa for the European Union (EFSA Panel on Plant Health, 2024). For a complete discussion of results and conclusions of the present analysis, please refer to the related Scientific Opinion cited above.

3. Data and methodologies

3.1. Systematic literature search & pest distribution

Table 1 shows the search strings used in both Web of Science and Scopus literature databases to retrieve references on both *L. orbonalis* and African *Leucinodes* spp. No distinct search was made for the African species, but a single common search was conducted for *L. orbonalis* and the species of *Leucinodes* occurring in Africa.

Table 1: Search strings used, and queries results found in Web of Science and Scopus (Rossi et al., 2023).

Platform	Date of search	Query	N of documents
Web of Science	12/12/2022	TS=("Leucinodes orbonalis" OR "Leucinodes pseudorbonalis" OR "Leucinodes" OR "Pycnarmon discerptalis" OR "eggplant fruit borer" OR "brinjal fruit borer" OR "foreuse des solanées" OR "Auberginenfruchtbohrer" OR "brinjal fruit and shoot borer" OR "eggplant fruit and shoot borer" OR "Foreuse des solanées")	1446
Scopus	12/12/2022	TITLE-ABS-KEY("Leucinodes orbonalis" OR "Leucinodes pseudorbonalis" OR "Leucinodes" OR "Pycnarmon discerptalis" OR "eggplant fruit borer" OR "brinjal fruit borer" OR "foreuse des solanées" OR "Auberginenfruchtbohrer" OR "brinjal fruit and shoot borer" OR "eggplant fruit and shoot borer" OR "Foreuse des solanées")	897

3.2. Document screening and data extraction

Document screening was performed using the software DistillerSR (Evidence Partners, 2022) and followed a two-step approach: Title and abstract (TIAB), and Full Text data extraction. While most references report *L. orbonalis* as widely distributed in the African continent, a paper from

Mally et al. (2015) demonstrates, through morphological methods and DNA barcoding, that *L. orbonalis* does not occur in Africa. In fact, all specimens collected in the study of Mally et al. (2015) were identified as belonging to eight different species, namely *Leucinodes africanensis*, *L. ethiopica*, *L. kenyensis*, *L. laisalis*, *L. malawiensis*, *L. pseudorbonalis*, *L. rimavallis*, and *L. ugandensis*. Therefore, in the data extraction phase (Table 2), literature containing either clear references to the African continent or observations recorded in Africa were regarded as reports on African *Leucinodes* spp. All other references (i.e. those not clearly indicating the origin of the specimens as from Africa) were discarded. An exception was made for points recorded in Europe, Saudi Arabia, and Iran (see Results section), which were included in the analysis (see below).

Table 2: Information and data extracted from the literature and collected in the master file.

Field name	Description	Type
<i>Refid</i>	Record ID. The Refid number is a unique number associated to each reference in Distiller	Integer
<i>Reference</i>	Full reference for the record	String
<i>Source type</i>	Categorises the type of reference. Available options: original study, review study, distribution map, other	String
<i>Distribution</i>	Presence of information on distribution (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Physiology_Ecology</i>	Presence of information on physiology and/or ecology (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>T</i>	Presence of information on temperature (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>RH</i>	Presence of information on humidity or moisture (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Photoperiod</i>	Presence of information on photoperiod (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Host</i>	Presence of information on host availability (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Biology</i>	Presence of information on pest biology (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Impact</i>	Presence of information on the impact of the pest (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Spread</i>	Presence of information on the spread of the pest (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean
<i>Control Methods</i>	Presence of information on control methods used against the pest (indicated through "x"). Empty means no information	Boolean

Fourty one records of observations of *L. laisalis* in Europe were retrieved from Mally et al. (2015), Huertas Dionisio (2000), and online databases: INaturalist (<https://www.inaturalist.org/>), Biodiversitydata (<https://data.biodiversitydata.nl/>), Lepiforum (<https://lepiforum.org/>).

3.3. Data analysis

3.3.1. Köppen–Geiger climate classification analysis

The SCAN-Clim tool (EFSA & Maiorano, 2022) was used to develop climate suitability maps based on the Köppen–Geiger climate classification from Kottek et al. (2006) after the re-analysis of Rubel et al. (2017), for the period 1986–2010 (available at <http://koeppen-geiger.vu-wien.ac.at/present.htm>). The climate types present in the observed locations of African *Leucinodes* spp. Were identified and mapped. Since the area of the assessment is the EU, the output maps considered only climate types that are also present in Europe. The Köppen–Geiger map was created using only point observations (identified through coordinates) as input presence data.

3.3.2. CLIMEX

The CLIMEX software (version 4.1.0.0, Kriticos et al., 2015) was used to infer the suitability of African *Leucinodes* spp. in the EU. The few data on the ecophysiology of African species of *Leucinodes* retrieved from the literature was fragmented and reported as for *L. orbonalis*. Hence, as a first test, and after verification of the results, the same CLIMEX parameterization of the assessment of the related Asian species (i.e., *L. orbonalis*) was used (Rossi et al., 2023, paragraph 3.2.5). This was done based on the assumption that African *Leucinodes* spp. would have similar eco-physiological requirements to the Asian species. This assumption was verified by visual inspection of the correspondence of presence locations of African species of *Leucinodes* and the CLIMEX map for Africa based on *L. orbonalis* parameters (see below). The prediction map of African *Leucinodes* species in Europe is then identical to the prediction map of *L. orbonalis*. Simulations were run using the climate dataset *CM30 1995H V2 WO* (Kriticos et al., 2011) at a spatial resolution of 0.5° (available at: <https://www.climond.org/>) to calculate the CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI). Table 3 summarises the model parameterisation used for the simulations.

The potential effects of climate change on the climate suitability of African *Leucinodes* spp. in the EU were assessed for the period 2040–2059. The outputs of four regional climate models (i.e., ACCESS 1.0, CNRM-CM5, GFDL-ESM-2M, and NorESM1-M, available at: <https://www.climond.org/Core/Authenticated/Climex.aspx>) for the representative emission scenario RCP8.5 (“business as usual”), were used as input climate data. A CLIMEX simulation was run for each regional climate model maintaining the species-specific model parameterisation of the current scenario. A CLIMEX simulation ensemble was created averaging the EI of each individual simulation (hereafter Climate Change scenario). The effect of climate change on the potential climate suitability of the species complex was assessed as the change of EI in the Climate Change scenario compared to the current climate scenario.

3.3.3. Identification of NUTS2 regions in Europe

The results of the CLIMEX models were then used to calculate for each EU NUTS2 region the number of CLIMEX pixels (0.5°) with $EI \geq 1$ as well as the total number of pixels for both the current climate and the Climate Change scenario. The same was done for $EI \geq 15$ and $EI \geq 30$.

Table 3: CLIMEX parameterization used in both the current climate and climate change scenarios (Rossi et al., 2023).

Class	Parameter	Description	Parameter value	Source (RefID*)
Temperature index	DV0	Lower temperature threshold	15°C	315
	DV1	Lower optimal temperature	26°C	24, 315, 1861
	DV2	Upper optimal temperature	38°C	24, 315, 1833
	DV3	Upper temperature threshold	39°C	1683
Cold stress	TTCS**	Cold stress temperature threshold	5.13°C	**
	THCS**	Cold stress accumulation rate	-0.00237 week ⁻¹	**
	DTCS	Cold stress will begin to accumulate when this threshold number of degree-days above DVCS is not achieved.	2°C	Iteration
	DHCS	Rate at which Cold Stress accumulates once the threshold number of degree-days above DVCS (DTCS) is not achieved	-0.001 week ⁻¹	Iteration
	TTCSA	Average weekly temperature below which Cold Stress accumulates.	0°C	Iteration
	THCSA	Rate at which Cold Stress accumulates once temperatures drop below the threshold value of TTCS1.	0°C	Iteration
Heat stress	TTHS	Heat stress temperature threshold	39°C	1683
	THHS	Heat stress accumulation rate	0.001 week ⁻¹	Iteration
	DTHS	Heat stress will begin to accumulate when this threshold number of degree-days above DV3 is exceeded.	0°C	Iteration
	DHHS	This is the rate at which Heat Stress accumulates once the threshold number of degree-days above DV3 (DTHS) is exceeded	0°C	Iteration
Dry stress	SMDS**	Dry stress soil moisture value	0.09797	**
	HDS**	Dry stress soil moisture rate	-0.00782 week ⁻¹	**
Wet stress	SMWS	Soil moisture wet stress threshold	4	Iteration
	HDS	Wet stress accumulation rate	0.001 week ⁻¹	Iteration
DD above DV0	DV0	Lower temperature threshold	15°C	315
	DV3	Upper temperature threshold	39°C	1683
DD above DVCS	DVCS**	Degree-days based cold stress	5.13°C	**
DD above DVHS	DVHS	Degree-days based heat stress	39°C	1683
Annual Heat sum	PDD***	Minimum degree day sum needed to complete a generation	438.6	***

* RefID is the key to the full list of reference available in African_Leucinodes_spp_ANNEX_A_Master_File.xlsx (10.5281/zenodo.10693734).

** Values retrieved using the built-in CLIMEX genetic algorithm (version 4.1.0.0, Kriticos et al., 2015).

*** PDD was calculated with a linear regression model using life table studies data (Rossi et al., 2023).

4. Results

4.1. Document screening and data extraction

For the results of the literature search and document screening please refer to the *Leucinodes orbonalis* Zenodo repository (Rossi et al., 2023). Of the 573 documents analysed, 28 references included information on African *Leucinodes* spp. To these, 8 additional studies found online and not captured with the systematic literature search were added. The PRISMA diagram (Moher, Liberati, Tetzlaff, Altman, & PRISMA Group, 2009) (Figure 1) displays the outputs of the literature search steps followed for the *Leucinodes* species complex from Africa. The asterisk (*) indicates the steps developed in the document screening of *Leucinodes orbonalis* from Asia (Rossi et al., 2023).

All of the 36 references analysed contained information on the distribution of African *Leucinodes* spp., 23 had information on the hosts, five reported physio-ecological requirements, eleven contained information on the biology, impact and spread were reported in 16 and 3 references respectively, and control methods appeared in 16 studies. A complete list of all the publications that were used in this study, including their RefIDs is available in Zenodo ([African_Leucinodes_spp_ANNEX_A_Master_File.xlsx](#)).

Figure 1: PRISMA Diagram describing the process followed to identify, screen, and include eligible information on the distribution, hosts, physio-ecology, biology, impact, spread, and control methods of the pest African *Leucinodes* spp.

4.2. Pest distribution

In total, 145 presence observations were retrieved from the 36 selected publications (Figure 2 and Figure 3 on the left), including 32 records on presence in administrative units and 113 records reporting presence at point locations described by coordinates. Out of the 113 point locations, 84 were previously identified by Mally et al. (2015), seven came from additional documents not included in the results of the systematic literature search, and the remaining 22 were extracted from the other references (n = 5) selected. The list of all extracted locations is available in two Excel files in Zenodo ([African_Leucinodes_spp_ANNEX_B_Observation_File.xlsx](#) and [African_Leucinodes_spp_ANNEX_C_L_laisalis_Europe.xlsx](#)).

Leucinodes spp. are widely distributed in sub-Saharan Africa. Nigeria, Ghana, Uganda, and Kenya are the countries with the greatest number of presence observations, accounting for more than 50% of the recorded observations. Only three observations of African species of *Leucinodes* do not come from sub-Saharan Africa: one in Saudi Arabia (*Leucinodes ethiopica*), one in Morocco (*Leucinodes laisalis*), and one in Spain (*Leucinodes laisalis*), all referenced in Mally et al. (2015). An observation of *Leucinodes* from Iran, identified in the literature as *L. orbonalis*, was also included (Rezaei & Dargahi, 2004). In addition, 41 observation points of *L. laisalis* originating from European publications (Huertas Dionisio, 2000; Mally et al., 2015) and online databases (iNaturalist.org, Lepiforum.org, and Biodiversitydata, see section 3.2.) were added. These presence points were on the coast of Spain and Portugal (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Observed distribution of African *Leucinodes* spp. at country level. Grey polygons illustrate those countries where at least one point location or administrative unit reported the presence of African *Leucinodes* spp.

Figure 3: Observed distribution of African *Leucinodes* spp. The map shows both point observations (with coordinates) where African *Leucinodes* spp. were reported. Administrative units are indicated only if point observations in that unit were not available. Different colours identify the different species. Regarding the administrative units, no information on the specific species was available in the literature. Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN. Cartography: EFSA 02/2024

4.3. Köppen–Geiger climate matching

From the Köppen–Geiger map created using point locations, the observation in Iran is the only one under the BSk climate (cold semi-arid), while the Cfb climate (Temperate oceanic climate or subtropical highland climate) is present due to one point in Eritrea and five points in Kenya (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Köppen-Geiger climate matching for Europe and the African continent. BSh = Hot semi-arid climate; BSk = cold semi-arid; Cfa = Humid subtropical climate; Csa = Hot-summer Mediterranean climate. The two zooms on the right, Eritrea and Kenya, show the six points falling under Cfb climate type (Temperate oceanic climate or subtropical highland climate). Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN. Cartography: EFSA 02/2024.

4.4. CLIMEX

4.4.1. Current climate scenario

The five references containing information on the ecophysiology of the African *Leucinodes* complex report temperatures ranging from 22 to 32°C, with optimum between 27–32°C (Aina, 1984; Emeasor & Uwalaka, 2018; Nwana, 1992; Onekutu et al., 2013). Figure 5 shows the data from Dhaliwal and Aggarwal (2021) which were used in the parameterization of CLIMEX for the Asian species *L. orbonalis*. The yellow point is the only ecophysiological datum found in the literature reporting a development time for an African species of *Leucinodes* (Onekutu et al., 2013). The reference states: "Developmental biology of *Leucinodes orbonalis* guenee: At room temperature of 27-32°C and relative humidity of 85-92% inside plastic cages kept in the laboratory. Developmental stages consist of one egg, five larval instars, pupa and adult. The mean life cycle of *Leucinodes orbonalis* on *Solanum gilio* [A/N *Solanum aethiopicum*] fruits from egg to adult was 28.17 days, with a range of 24-46 days at fluctuating room temperature and 85-92% relative humidity." (Onekutu et al., 2013). The study was conducted at the Entomology Research Laboratory of the Department of Crop Protection and Environmental Biology of the University of Ibadan, Nigeria, and therefore considered to be a study on an African species of *Leucinodes*.

Figure 5: Black points represent the developmental rate from egg to adult at different constant temperatures (°C) (Kaur Dhaliwal et al., 2020) of *Leucinodes orbonalis* in Asia. The yellow point represents the datum from the only reference reporting development time from egg to adult of an African specimens from Nigeria, reported as *Leucinodes orbonalis* (Onekutu et al., 2013).

The development time found in Onekutu et al. (2013) was registered for the average temperature of the experiment (minimum temperature 27°C, maximum temperature 32°C, average 29.5°C) and expressed as development rate in Figure 5. These findings support the assumption that the African *Leucinodes* species have temperature requirements similar to the Asian species *L. orbonalis*.

The results of the CLIMEX simulation under current climate describe the distribution of African *Leucinodes* species well (Figure 6). The Ecoclimatic Index is higher than 30 in almost all the distribution points, where an EI of 30 is a threshold for 'good suitability' according to CLIMEX developers (Kriticos et al., 2011). Only three locations (one in South Africa, the one in Saudi Arabia, and the one in Iran) had EI=0. For all the other locations the minimum EI was 33, registered in Daleti, Ethiopia. The observations of *L. laisalis* in Europe showed a minimum EI of 28 and a maximum EI of 41.

In Europe, the simulation showed a higher risk of establishment in the Mediterranean coasts, especially in Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Spain, and Portugal. In conclusion, the areas where the climate suitability is highest are the warm areas on the coast of the Mediterranean Sea, while inland areas of Spain, France, Italy, and most of the Portuguese territory showed a lower suitability.

Figure 6: Left: CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI) in the area of distribution of African *Leucinodes* spp. Right: CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI) of *Leucinodes* spp. in Europe. Darker colours suggest more favourable conditions for establishment (higher EI). Points indicate coordinates of observed locations and colours differentiate the species recorded. Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN. Cartography: EFSA 02/2024.

4.4.2. Climate change scenarios

The climate change scenario (Fig. 7, right panel) resulted in an increase in potential climate suitability compared to the current climate scenario (Figure 6, right panel), with a northward expansion of the potentially suitable areas. An increase in suitable area is most conspicuous in the North-West of France, in Spain, where most of the territory becomes potentially suitable for establishment, and in Portugal. Also, in Greece and Italy there was an increase in potentially suitable area.

Figure 7 (right panel) shows the standard deviation of the EI based on the four regional climate models (APPENDIX A, Figure A.1) compared to their average in Figure 7 left. The map highlights a relatively high variability among the EIs calculated with different climate models, especially in Spain, Italy, Greece, Turkey, and North Africa.

Figure 8 shows the increase in the areas with $EI \geq 1$ (left panel) and the relative change (right panel), expressed as percentage (%) of the climate change scenario compared to the current climate conditions (right panel). With climate change, there is a northward expansion of the potentially suitable areas.

Figure 7: Ensemble prediction of the CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI) of African *Leucinodes* spp. in Europe under climate change. Darker colours suggest more favourable conditions for establishment (higher EI), figure on the left. On the right, the standard deviation of the average of the Ecoclimatic Index (EI) of the four climate change scenarios. Darker colours indicate a greater standard deviation. Points indicate coordinates of observed locations. Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN. Cartography: EFSA 02/2024.

Figure 8: Areas in Europe with Ecoclimatic Index (EI) ≥ 1 comparing the average EI calculated under four climate change scenarios (in dark red) with the current climate scenario (in yellow), panel on the left. Relative change (%) in average Ecoclimatic Index (EI) under climate change compared to EI with current climate. Red and blue shades indicate percentual increases and

decreases, respectively, in EI. Points indicate presence locations of *L. laisalis* in Europe. Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN. Cartography: EFSA 02/2024.

Figure 9: Areas with Ecoclimatic Index equal to or higher than three EI thresholds (i.e., $EI \geq 1$, $EI \geq 15$, $EI \geq 30$). The panel on the left shows EI with current climate, while the panel on the right shows the ensemble prediction under climate change. Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN. Cartography: EFSA 02/2024.

4.5. Identification of NUTS2 regions at potential risk of establishment

Figure 10 shows those NUTS2 regions containing at least one pixel, or a fraction of a pixel, with EI equal or higher than 1, 15, and 30, both in the current climate (left) and under climate change (right). The number of regions with $EI \geq 1$ in current climate is 82, which increases to 121 if climate change scenario is considered, where greater areas in the north of France, Italy, Spain, Greece, Bulgaria, and Turkey have $EI \geq 1$. Similar patterns are registered also with $EI \geq 15$ and $EI \geq 30$, where the regions with $EI \geq 15$ increase to 88 and those with $EI \geq 30$ increase to 61, compared to the 62 and 36 regions, respectively, in the current climate scenario.

Figure 10: NUTS2 regions containing at least one pixel (or a fraction of a pixel) with Ecoclimatic Index (EI) of $EI \geq 1$, $EI \geq 15$, and $EI \geq 30$. The panel on the left shows NUTS2 areas with $EI \geq 1$, ≥ 15 or ≥ 30 with current climate scenario, while the panel on the right shows the results under climate change. Points indicate observed presence locations of *Leucinodes laisalis* in Spain and Portugal. Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN. Cartography: EFSA 02/2024.

References

- Aina, J. O. (1984). The biology of *Daraba laisalis* (Wlk) formerly called *Sceliodes laisalis* (Wlk) (Pyralidae, Lepidoptera), an egg fruit borer. *International Journal of Tropical Insect Science*, 5(6), 513-520.
- Devorshak, C. (2012). *Plant pest risk analysis: concepts and application*.
- Dhaliwal, N. K., & Aggarwal, N. (2021). Development and survival of brinjal shoot and fruit borer *Leucinodes orbonalis* Guenee (Crambidae: Lepidoptera) at constant and alternating temperatures [Article]. *International Journal of Tropical Insect Science*, 41(2), 1717-1728. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42690-020-00376-5>
- EFSA. (2010). Application of systematic review methodology to food and feed safety assessments to support decision making. *EFSA Journal*, 8(6). <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2010.1637>
- EFSA, & Maiorano, A. (2022). SCAN-Clim: a tool to support pest climate suitability analysis based on climate classification. *EFSA Journal*, 20(2), e07104. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7104>
- EFSA PLH Panel (EFSA Panel on Plant Health), Bragard, C., Baptista, P., Chatzivassiliou, E., Di Serio, F., Gonthier, P., Jaques Miret, J. A., Justesen, A. F., MacLeod, A., Magnusson, C. S., Milonas, P., Navas-Cortes, J. A., Parnell, S., Potting, R., Reignault, P. L., Stefani, E., Thulke, H.-H., Civera, A. V., Yuen, J., ... Van der Werf, W. (2024). Pest risk assessment of African *Leucinodes* species for the European Union. *EFSA Journal*, 22(4), e8739. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2024.8739>
- Emeasor, K. C., & Uwalaka, O. A. (2018). Control of fruit borer of garden egg *Leucinodes orbonalis* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) using organic and inorganic pesticides [article]. *Net Journal of Agricultural Science*, 6(2), 16-19. <https://doi.org/10.30918/njas.62.17.063>
- Evidence Partners. (2022). *DistillerSR*. In (Version 2.43) Distiller Inc.
- IPPC. (2013). *ISPM 11. Pest risk analysis for quarantine pests*. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/handle/20.500.14283/11302E>
- Kottek, M., Grieser, J., Beck, C., Rudolf, B., & Rubel, F. (2006). World Map of the Köppen-Geiger climate classification updated. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift Vol. 15*, 259 - 263. https://opus.bibliothek.uni-augsburg.de/opus4/files/40083/metz_Vol_15_No_3_p259-263_World_Map_of_the_Koppen_Geiger_climate_classification_updated_55034.pdf
- Kriticos, D. J., Maywald, G. F., Yonow, T., Zurcher, E. J., Herrmann, N. I., & Sutherst, R. W. (2015). *CLIMEX Version 4: Exploring the effects of climate on plants, animals and diseases*. CSIRO. In (Version 4.1.0.0) Canberra. 156 pp.
- Kriticos, D. J., Webber, B. L., Leriche, A., Ota, N., Macadam, I., Bathols, J., & Scott, J. K. (2011). CliMond: global high-resolution historical and future scenario climate surfaces for bioclimatic modelling. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 3(1), 53-64. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2041-210X.2011.00134.x>
- Mally, R., Korycinska, A., Agassiz, D. J. L., Hall, J., Hodgetts, J., & Nuss, M. (2015). Discovery of an unknown diversity of *Leucinodes* species damaging Solanaceae fruits in sub-Saharan Africa and moving in trade (Insecta, Lepidoptera, Pyraloidea) [Review]. *Zookeys*(472), 117-162. <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.472.8781>
- Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., Altman, D. G., & PRISMA Group. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: the PRISMA statement. *Annals of internal medicine*, 151(4), 264-269.
- Nwana, I. E. (1992). The biology and seasonal occurrence of *Leucinodes orbonalis* Guenee (Lepidoptera: Pyraustidae), the fruit- and shoot-borer of eggplant, *Solanum melongena* Linnaeus in southeastern Nigeria [Article]. *Bulletin of Entomology*, 33(1-2), 32-41. <Go to ISI>://ZOOREC:ZOOR13400050459
- Onekutu, A., Omoloye, A. A., & Odebisi, J. A. (2013). Biology of the Eggfruit and Shoot Borer (EFSB), *Leucinodes orbonalis* Guenee (Crambidae) on the Garden Egg, *Solanum gilo* Raddi [Article]. *Journal of Entomology*, 10(3), 156-162. <https://doi.org/10.3923/je.2013.156.162>
- Rezaei, V. & Dargahi, M. (2004): The first report of eggplant fruit borer *Leucinodes orbonalis* Guenée, 1854 (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) from Iran. – In: Proceedings of the 16th Iranian Plant Protection Congress, p. 142; Tabriz (University of Tabriz).
- Rossi, E., Gobbi, A., Czwienczek, E., Lopez Mercadal, J., Van der Werf, W., MacLeod, A., Mally, R., De Santis, M., Stancanelli, G., & Maiorano, A. (2023). *EFSA Climate Suitability Analysis of Leucinodes orbonalis*.
- Rubel, F., Brugger, K., Haslinger, K., & Auer, I. (2017). The climate of the European Alps: Shift of very high resolution Köppen-Geiger climate zones 1800–2100. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift.*, 26, 115-125. . <https://doi.org/10.1127/metz/2016/0816>.

Content of the African *Leucinodes* spp. Zenodo repository

African_Leucinodes_spp_literature_search_climate_suitability.pdf

The file contains the methodology and results of the Climate Suitability Analysis for African *Leucinodes* spp., describing the extensive literature search and the climate classification. The results of the database interrogations are presented together with the process applied for documents screening and selection, summarised by a PRISMA diagram. Maps illustrate the pest distribution and the results of the climate suitability analyses. Although, we refer to the related PRA (EFSA Panel on Plant Health, 2024) for an exhaustive and detailed discussion of the results.

African_Leucinodes_spp_ANNEX_A_Master_file.xlsx

The file contains the list of documents selected for data extraction. The description of the fields is in *African_Leucinodes_spp_literature_search_climate_suitability.pdf*.

African_Leucinodes_spp_ANNEX_B_Observations.xlsx

The file contains the observed distribution at a global level. Both point locations and administrative units are included.

African_Leucinodes_spp_ANNEX_C_L_laisalis_Europe.csv

The file contains the observed distribution of *Leucinodes laisalis* in Spain and Portugal.

Maps in .jpeg format

- *African_Leucinodes_spp_Absolute_relative_change_EI.jpeg*
- *African_Leucinodes_spp_CLIMEX_Current_climate_Distribution.jpeg*
- *African_Leucinodes_spp_CLIMEX_EI_CC_AVG_SD.jpeg*
- *African_Leucinodes_spp_CLIMEX_EI_Current_Climate_Europe.jpeg*
- *African_Leucinodes_spp_Distribution_Map.jpeg*
- *African_Leucinodes_spp_Distribution_africa_and_laislis_Europe.jpeg*
- *African_Leucinodes_spp_Distribution_only_africa.jpeg*
- *African_Leucinodes_spp_Four_cc_models.jpeg*
- *African_Leucinodes_spp_KG_points.jpeg*
- *African_Leucinodes_spp_NUTS2_regions.jpeg*
- *African_Leucinodes_spp_thresholds_EI.jpeg*
- *African_Leucinodes_spp_NUTS2_different_EI.jpeg*

Leucinodes_spp_from_Africa.gpkg

GeoPackage (.gpkg) file containing the GIS layers of the results of the analysis.

Short title

African_Leucinodes_spp_QGIS_Styles.zip

QGIS styles to replicate the symbology used in the maps published in the PRA. These styles were applied to the layers contained in African_Leucinodes_spp_PRA.gpkg

Appendix A – Additional figures

The outputs of four regional climate models (i.e., ACCESS 1.0, CNRM-CM5, GFDL-ESM-2M, and NorESM1-M, available at: <https://www.climond.org/Core/Authenticated/Climex.aspx>) for the representative emission scenario RCP8.5 (“business as usual”), were used as input climate data in CLIMEX (Kriticos et al., 2012) to produce the climate change ensemble scenario. Figure A.1 shows the Ecoclimatic Index of the CLIMEX simulations for the four regional climate change models used.

Figure A.A.1: CLIMEX simulations of the four regional climate models for the relative near-term period 2040–2059 at the RCP8.5 “business as usual” scenario. Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN. Cartography: EFSA 02/2024.

Figure A.2 left shows that the NUTS2 regions with the highest percentage of pixels with potentially suitable conditions ($EI \geq 1$) in current climate conditions are concentrated on the Mediterranean coast and in Portugal. More specifically, 100% of pixels with $EI \geq 1$ were registered in Kypros, Ionia Nisia, Dytiki Ellada, Voreio Aigaio, Regio Autnoma dos Aores, Kriti, Sicilia, Regin de Murcia, Ciudad de Ceuta, Ciudad de Melilla, Sardegna, Pas Vasco, Canarias, Alentejo, Malta, Centro (PT), Algarve, rea Metropolitana de Lisboa, Puglia, Calabria, Liguria, İstanbul.

Attiki, Região Autónoma da Madeira, Illes Balears, Notio Aigaiio, Extremadura, Lazio, Andalucía, Campania have a percentage of pixels higher than 85%.

If the climate change scenario is considered (Figure 8 right), the number of NUTS2 regions with $EI \geq 1$ increases from the 82 of the current climate conditions to 121. The change is particularly evident in the number of regions with more than 85% of pixels with $EI \geq 1$, that increase from 35 in the current climate conditions to 59 in the climate change scenario. In considering only the NUTS2 regions with 100% of pixels with $EI \geq 1$, they increase to 44, compared to the 26 under current climate conditions. Similar increases in number of NUTS2 regions are visible considering higher EI as thresholds (i.e., 15 and 30) in Figures A.4 and A.5, respectively.

Figure A.2: Percentage (%) of pixels (0.5°) per NUTS2 of EFTA, candidate countries, and EU member states, with $EI \geq 1$, in current climate conditions (on the left) and in climate change conditions (on the right). Darker colours suggest a higher percentage of pixels with $EI \geq 1$. Points indicate coordinates of observed locations. Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN. Cartography: EFSA 02/2024.

Figure A.3: Percentage (%) of pixels (0.5°) per NUTS2 of EFTA, candidate countries, and EU member states, with $EI \geq 15$, in current climate conditions (on the left) and in climate change conditions (on the right). Darker colours suggest a higher percentage of pixels with $EI \geq 15$. Points indicate coordinates of observed locations. Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN. Cartography: EFSA 02/2024.

Figure A.4: Percentage (%) of pixels (0.5°) per NUTS2 of EFTA, candidate countries, and EU member states, with $EI \geq 30$, in current climate conditions (on the left) and in climate change conditions (on the right). Darker colours suggest a higher percentage of pixels with $EI \geq 30$. Points indicate coordinates of observed locations. Administrative boundaries: © FAO-UN. Cartography: EFSA 02/2024.